

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

Registration form (basic details)

1a. Details of applicant

Title: dr.

First name: Hannes

Initials: H.

Prefix:

Surname: Datta

Male/female: male

Address for correspondence: Department of Marketing
Tilburg School of Economics and Management
Tilburg University
Office K1030
PO Box 90153
5000 LE Tilburg

Preference for correspondence in English: no

Telephone: +31 13 466 8938

Cell phone: +31 6 57194162

Email: h.datta@uvt.nl

Website (optional): www.datta-online.de

Use of extension clause (see Notes): no

1b. Title of research proposal

The Sharing Economy: Societal Implications of Online Streaming

1c. Scientific summary of research proposal (Max. 300 words)

Consumers increasingly give up ownership in favor of access, e.g., by sharing cars or tools, instead of buying them. Consumer adoption of access is especially prominent for information goods. Specifically, online streaming—a business strategy of renting rather than selling a bundle of products—has become a dominant form of distribution in industries such as music, movies, books, and software. However, academic research remains scarce. The goal of this research program is to investigate the demand- and supply-side effects of the transition from ownership to streaming, using data from the music industry. The proposal contains 3 parts formulated as interlinked projects.

Projects 1 and 2 explore the welfare implications for consumers as a result of adopting streaming. In project 1, I investigate how streaming affects consumers' quantity and variety of music consumption. Because the price of consuming extra variety falls to zero (barring psychological costs), consumers may re-allocate their listening across artists, or engage into more discovery (potentially to the benefit of smaller artists). In project 2, I investigate consumers' switching costs after adopting online streaming. By renting, rather than buying, content access hinges on paying monthly subscription fees, and may hence create "lock-in" effects that make it costly for consumers to disadopt. How do consumers cope with these switching costs? How sensitive are consumers to (re)adopt piracy as a form of content acquisition?

Finally, project 3 investigates how streaming affects the supply of new music. Streaming generates revenues over extended consumption histories, instead of once at the moment of purchase. This may affect artists' production incentives (e.g., decelerating production in some genres), and release schedules (e.g., withholding content for some consumers). The results of the studies will be insightful for consumer welfare, content providers, platforms, and public policy makers. [290 words]

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

1d. Keywords (Max. five keywords)

- Online Streaming
- Sharing Economy
- Music Consumption
- Econometrics

1e. Current institution of employment

Tilburg University

1f. Prospective host institution (If known)

Tilburg University

1g. NWO Division (Choose one)

Interdivisional*	
ALW	
CW	
EW	
GW	
MaGW	X
ZonMw	
N	
STW	

* **Explanation of the interdivisional character of the proposal** (only to be filled out if you have chosen to submit your application as interdivisional, 50-100 words): N/A

1h. Main field of research (see notes)

If applicable: other fields of research, in order of relevance

Code	Main field of research
39.90.00	Business Administration
	Other fields of research (if applicable)

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

1i. Public summary of your research proposal

(In Dutch and in English, max. 50 words each, see notes).

English:

Title: The Sharing Economy: Societal Implications of Online Streaming
Personal details: Dr. H. (Hannes) Datta (m), Tilburg University -
Tilburg School of Economics and Management
Summary: Consumers increasingly give up ownership in favor of access.
However, academic research on the access-based economy is scarce.
This project systematically investigates how access-based business
models—particularly streaming services for information goods (e.g.,
music)—affect consumers, content owners, platforms, and public
policy makers. [43 words]

Dutch:

Title: De deeleconomie: gevolgen voor de samenleving van online streaming
Personal details: Dr. H. (Hannes) Datta (m), Universiteit van Tilburg -
Tilburg School of Economics and Management
Summary: Consumenten geven steeds vaker eigendom op ten gunste van
toegang via abonnementen. Echter, momenteel is er slechts weinig
onderzoek naar dit fenomeen. De auteur zal onderzoek verrichten
naar abonnement-gebaseerde businessmodellen—met name over
streaming diensten voor informatiegoederen (b.v. muziek)—en hoe
deze consumenten, producenten, platforms, en beleidsmakers gaan
beïnvloeden. [49 words]

Research proposal

2a1 and 2a2. Description of the proposed research

(max. 2000 words on no more than 6 pages, see Notes)

Scientific relevance and challenges

Technological progress has enabled consumers to give up ownership in favor of access: consumers share cars (e.g., on snappcar.nl), parking space (e.g., on drivemoby.nl), and tools (e.g., on peerby.nl), instead of buying them. In the sharing economy, service providers alleviate consumers from the deadweight loss of owning products, hence saving up public goods (e.g., clean air, inner-city space), or keeping consumers from unnecessary expenditures (e.g., buying an infrequently used drill). With a projected revenue increase from USD\$15B to USD\$335B from 2015 to 2025, providing access over ownership is among the most promising business-model innovations of the recent years [1].

An important development in the context of access over ownership, and the focus of this research proposal, concerns online streaming. Streaming represents a business strategy of on-demand consumption of digital content on a subscription, rather than purchasing products. For example, the largest online streaming service for music, Spotify, offers consumers access to 30 million songs at a subscription fee of about €10 per month. In the old model of buying music, €10 would have gotten the consumer a single album consisting of 10 songs.

Service providers from many industries embrace the streaming model: recorded music (e.g., Spotify, Apple Music), live concerts and opera (e.g., Het Concertgebouw, Berlin Philharmonic Orchestra), movies (e.g., Netflix, Pathé Thuis), books (e.g., Kindle Unlimited), newspapers and magazines (e.g., New York Times), software (e.g., Office 365, Salesforce), and games (e.g., Steam). Given the growth of these industries, consumers seemingly extract more value from access-based consumption than from purchasing alone. Interestingly, the Netherlands—the gateway for digital innovation in Europe [2]—is a particular growth market for streaming services. As Dutch consumers are increasingly exposed to this form of digital innovation, investigating the societal effects of streaming becomes central.

The question at the core of this research program is how streaming alters consumer behavior and affects its stakeholders: consumers, content owners, platforms, and public policy makers. Using data from the music industry, I investigate online streaming—one out of arguably many facets of the sharing economy—for two reasons: First, streaming is a new business model and many pressing questions are unanswered. An in-depth analysis would allow me to become an expert in this nascent field. Second, my experience with music consumption data opens up unique cooperations with leading organizations in this field (Buma/Stemra, and a confidential major label). Further, the music industry embraced streaming earlier than other industries, and provides sufficient historical data for my empirical work. Therefore, my findings can impact decision-making in related industries whose transition to online streaming is yet to evolve. In what follows, I will advance three interlinked projects:

Project 1. Demand and Variety Consumption in Online Streaming

In project 1, I study the demand-side effects of consumers' music consumption when migrating from an ownership model to a streaming service. Specifically, I investigate how this switch affects the quantity and variety of listening immediately following adoption, and in the long-term (6 months or longer after adoption). Since revenues in the streaming model are generated by consumption, and not purchase, determining how consumers re-allocate their listening is of vital importance to rights holders, and has important consequence for the structure of the industry. If consumers

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

consume only a few major artists, they perpetuate the winner-take-all market, favoring superstars. If, on the other hand, consumers now broaden their consumption, streaming services may balance competition to the benefit of small, independent labels [3].

First, I ask to what extent streaming services generate additional music consumption rather than displacing consumption from other platforms. For example, access to increased variety on streaming services may cause overall consumption to grow. Second, I investigate the consequences of streaming for variety in consumers' choices by measuring its breadth (e.g., total number of artists, songs, and genres), concentration (e.g., superstars [4, 5]), discovery of new music, and repeat consumption.

Preliminary evidence based upon a difference-in-difference estimator indicate a long-term fragmentation of consumers' listening from choosing more variety and engaging in less repeat listening when adopting the access model. Also, consumers discover more new music, balancing the playing field in favor of small artists. Last, streaming may not only draw consumption from ownership-based business models [6], but potentially leads to growth in overall consumption of music.

Project 2. Switching Costs of Online Streaming: Implications for Consumer Welfare

When adopting streaming, consumers rent music rather than buy it. Hence, content access hinges on paying monthly subscription fees. If consumers disadopt, access to music libraries is restricted at best or disabled completely. Not owning any content, disadoption becomes prohibitively expensive. The goal of project 2 is to understand what drives these costs to disadoption—commonly referred to as switching costs in the literature—and investigate how consumers cope with limited content access.

Using joint choice/quantity models, I first investigate what drives switching costs (e.g., users' prior consumption histories, and demographic characteristics). Second, I study what consumers will listen to once they disadopt streaming. On the one hand, they may "re"-purchase content discovered via streaming. On the other hand, because of increased costs to re-acquisition, consumers may revert back to their potentially outdated music library, reducing any welfare effects accumulated via streaming (cf. project 1). Third, I examine how consumers will obtain content: legally, or illegally. If consumers largely pirate content, it may be risky for right holders to stop fighting piracy. Alternatively, if consumers mostly use legal channels, content providers may extract excess revenue at the expense of consumers by selling the same product twice: once on streaming via royalties-by-consumption, and once by re-acquisition. On a policy level, an evaluation of switching costs helps to inform competition-related questions of emerging platforms like Apple Music, Amazon Prime, and Spotify (cf. Directorate-General for Competition of the EU, and their focus on the distribution of information goods [7]).

Project 3. Supply-side Effects of Online Streaming

The effects of online piracy on demand for and supply of information goods have received ample attention in the literature [8-10]. Researchers largely agree that piracy reduces sales, while leaving supply of new products unaffected [11]. In project 3, I assess how online streaming affects the supply of new music. The key difference between the ownership model and streaming is its revenue generation mechanism: under the ownership model, revenues are generated every time a song or album is sold (zero in the case of piracy); online streaming, in contrast, generates revenue relative to (long-term) consumption, with three crucial consequences.

First, because royalties for frequently listened songs will be higher than royalties for rarely listened songs, an artist will earn more from an album's top song, than from average songs. An interesting question, hence, is how streaming affects the composition of product bundles (e.g., albums or playlists). For example, one could imagine that artists opt for smaller bundles, with higher average quality. Second, because royalties are paid *relative to current consumption*, an artist earns most royalties over the lifetime

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

of a song, instead of directly after its release. This long-term perspective in royalty payouts could affect producers of music, who may shift away from producing hits (high sales and high plays in only one period), to moderately famous songs (average sales and average plays, but over many periods). Third, because streaming services are still in an early stage, royalty payouts to artists are currently much lower than payouts from an album (e.g., \$0.01 per stream, but \$1 per sold track), and hence may not provide sufficient incentive to publish music.

Using a comprehensive data set (supplied by Buma/Stemra, NDA in preparation), I jointly model the evolution of demand and supply in the Dutch music industry using time series econometrics. This allows me to shed light on how streaming affects the supply of new music, and assess the development of the creative sector.

Project overview:

Originality and innovative character

- The projects are among the first academic studies to investigate the **effects of online streaming** on **demand** for, and **supply** of information goods
- Research on the sharing economy—and specifically online streaming—is **scarce**, allowing me to become an expert in this nascent field
- This project is at the **interface of data science and quantitative marketing**; with substantial technological spillovers to students and the academic community
- This project strives to be **open source**: code will be released for future use (completely for projects 1/2, and within the boundaries of an NDA for project 3).
- Online streaming is **highly debated in society**, and hence answering the research questions serves public interest. Further, the proposed projects are **timely** and my results can still be used to **raise awareness among the general public** about potential pitfalls of streaming

Methods and techniques

Data

For the first two projects, I make use of longitudinal data from a panel of music listeners. These data have been collected by myself using **web scraping technology** from a music recommendation service. The data has already been cleaned. For the third project, I collaborate with the **Dutch royalty-collecting organization Buma/Stemra**, who grant complete access to data on demand- and supply metrics (available at the individual song-writer and artist level; online and offline sales, and streams). The NDA for this data is in preparation.

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

Method

I will use state-of-the art methods in econometrics with a focus on addressing **selection** (i.e., the non-random assignment to treatment and control groups in the samples used), **endogeneity** (e.g., using instrumental variables or Gaussian Copulas), and **heterogeneity** (e.g., by way of mixing distributions and simulated maximum likelihood). Also, I combine various methods (e.g., difference-in-difference estimator in project 1, choice modeling in project 2, and time series techniques in project 3), all of which I have gained ample experience in prior projects.

Computing resources

This project is embedded in the data science strategy of Tilburg University; the data sets are impressive in volume (gigabytes) and scope (e.g., number of variables). I will make use of several computing resources: For building prototypes for collecting and analyzing data, I will use the **computer infrastructure at Tilburg University**. For scaling my methods to production, I will make use of the **national eInfrastructure**. I have already experience from prior projects on this infrastructure (grants e-infra130055 and e-infra140195). For data management, I will use the EU-based **Amazon Cloud**, as some of the services (e.g., NoSQL databases) are not available at the national level.

Timetable and work plan over the grant period

Project Phase	Year	Project 1			Project 2			Project 3		
		1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
Data collection		■			■			■		
Data preparation			■		■	■		■	■	
Analysis		■				■				■
First submission			■	■			■			
Knowledge dissemination				■			■			■

Local, National, and International Collaboration

My host institution provides an excellent fit with the proposed projects. Importantly, I have several collaborations that I can draw from. I work with Bart Bronnenberg (an expert on quantity/variety tradeoffs, cf. project 1), Marnik Dekimpe (an expert in time series analysis), and George Knox (an expert on stochastic models). Also outside of my department, I have several national and international academic contacts. I work with Harald van Heerde at Massey University in New Zealand, and Jan Benedict Steenkamp at UNC Chapel Hill, USA.

Next to my direct collaborators, I expect input from my colleagues Barbara Deleersnyder, Els Gijsbrechts, and Aurélie Lemmens (with regard to data analysis), and Rik Pieters and Anne Klesse (with regard to consumer behavior like measurement of variety). At the faculty level, I am a member of the Structural Economics Group, and colleagues Jaap Abbring and Tobias Klein can assist me to validate the assumptions of my models. At the University level, Prof. John Einmahl is an expert on extreme value theory, and can provide input for investigating the concentration of the music industry.

Last, I collaborate with leading businesses in my field of research (e.g., meeting top executives of a (confidential) major record label, and exchanging data with Buma/Stemra).

2b. Knowledge utilisation

(max. 750 words on no more than 2 pages, see Notes)

Potential

The results of my research will be of interest to an interdisciplinary readership of marketing, economics, industrial organization, and the creative industries. Its implications for a number of stakeholders are outlined below.

Academics and Institutions conducting research

The findings from this proposal are important for researchers and institutions conducting research with data collected online (e.g., **scraped data sets, data from social media**). For example, other disciplines such as management and economics are just starting to realize the potential of this data, and best practices of data processing are not yet established. To conduct my research, I will also have to **refine algorithms for text-based matching** of large data sets, which can be **re-used by other researchers**. Last, knowledge on solving selection problems, which are central to my studies, make an impact in my field, and could also spill over to related disciplines.

Platforms and Content Owners

Artists question the benefits of releasing content on streaming services. Hence, the projects will inform artists about the **value of new music discovery** on streaming, compared to ownership-based business models. Independent labels may specifically be interested in learning how the **concentration of the industry** may change. If consumers spread their consumption across a wider set of artists and engage in less repeat listening, streaming may balance competition in favor of smaller artists. Platforms, in turn, may use the insights to better understand consumer behavior on their services and optimize user experience, e.g., via playlists.

Stakeholders of the sharing economy

Streaming is only one part of the sharing economy, and findings of how access-based consumption affects demand and supply will be transferable to other industries. For example, the supply of new products is crucial for the existence of **content-rich industries** (such as **books** and **magazines**), and is of heightened public interest.

Public Policy Implications

Given the substantial subsidies allocated to the **production of cultural goods** (e.g., books), investigating how streaming changes demand for them becomes central. If consumption flattens out, then **subsidies** for (parts) of the assortment may be uncalled for. Also, some of our results may be transferrable to access-based models for physical goods (e.g., car sharing). Further, my research informs public policy makers how switching costs of emerging platforms like Apple Music **inhibit consumers in their choices**. If this is indeed the case, then they could consider raising awareness among consumers—similar to warning consumers about risky financial investments.

Implementation

Knowledge utilisation will occur in four stages: First, next to refining my research questions with direct collaborators (e.g., Bronnenberg, Dekimpe, Knox), I will involve **executives at leading organizations** (Buma/Stemra, and a (confidential) major record label; NDAs in preparation). Also, executives will **visit Tilburg University** for projects with students, and towards coordinating the research. I will further develop my ideas by **presenting in research seminars** here and abroad (e.g., an informal invitation by prof. Puneet Manchanda at the University of Michigan is pending). To incorporate the view of (young) consumers, I will have informal conversations with students in classes or during

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

thesis supervision.

Second, early research findings will be **presented to an industry audience**. In the past, I have presented my work at Eurosonic Noorderslag Conference and Paaspop Academy, two practitioner conferences with great reach in the creative industries. In this way, knowledge disseminates quickly to industry experts and can hence be implemented even before any paper is published. Typically, talks at these conferences are filmed and released to the public (e.g., on streaming websites such as YouTube).

Third, knowledge dissemination will occur once my papers are published, typically 3-4 years after starting a project. The premier outlet for knowledge dissemination are the academic journals in which I seek to publish. Also important are **national and international media outlets** contacted by Tilburg University's team of communication advisors. For example, my dissertation received substantial media attention in The Netherlands (e.g., Limburgse Dagblad, emerge.nl), and abroad (New Zealand Herald, stuff.co.nz), and generated new contacts with industry experts. I believe exciting channels to present findings to **consumers** are video blogs (e.g., on YouTube) and technology-oriented documentary TV series (e.g., VPRO Tegenlicht).

Fourth, long-term knowledge dissemination will occur by developing **teaching material** on the basis of my research. Case studies and data challenges will train students to get experience working with this kind of data. Because computer code will be released publicly, my work can be re-used by other researchers and practitioners to develop new products.

2c. Number of words used: section 2a 1,986 words (text: 1,953, figure: 33)
(max. 2000 words)

Number of words used: section 2b 729 (max. 750 words)

2d. Literature references

1. PricewaterhouseCoopers (2015). The Sharing Economy. Available from: <https://www.pwc.com/us/en/industry/entertainment-media/publications/consumer-intelligence-series/assets/pwc-cis-sharing-economy.pdf> [accessed: 22 December 2015].
2. Ministerie van Economische Zaken (2013). Strategisch aanvalsplan The Netherlands: Digital Gateway to Europe. Available from: <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/binaries/rijksoverheid/documenten/rapporten/2013/07/02/strategisch-aanvalsplan-the-netherlands-digital-gateway-to-europe/strategisch-aanvalsplan-the-netherlands-digital-gateway-to-europe.pdf> [accessed: 22 December 2015].
3. Kissel, C. (2015). Spotify listeners discover roughly 27 new artists a month 2015. Available from: <http://diffuser.fm/spotify-listeners-discover-roughly-27-new-artists-a-month/> [accessed: 22 December 2015].
4. Elberse, A. (2008), Should you invest in the long tail? *Harvard Business Review*, 86(7/8), p. 88-96.
5. Rosen, S. (1981), The Economics of Superstars. *American Economic Review*, 71(5), p. 845-858.
6. Aguiar, L. and J. Waldfogel (2015), Streaming reaches flood stage: Does Spotify stimulate or depress music sales? National Bureau of Economic Research.
7. European Commission (2013). Competition in the media sector. Available from: http://ec.europa.eu/competition/sectors/media/overview_en.html [accessed: 26 December 2015].
8. Oberholzer-Gee, F. and K. Strumpf (2007), The Effect of File Sharing on Record Sales: An Empirical Analysis. *Journal of Political Economy*, 115(1), p. 1-42.
9. Liebowitz, S.J. (2008), Testing File-Sharing's Impact by Examining Record Sales in Cities. *Management Science*, 54(4), p. 852-859.
10. Rob, R. and J. Waldfogel (2006), Piracy on the High C's: Music Downloading, Sales Displacement, and Social Welfare in a Sample of College Students. *Journal of Law and Economics*, 49(1), p. 29-62.
11. Waldfogel, J. (2012), Music Piracy and Its Effects on Demand, Supply, and Welfare. National Bureau of Economic Research.

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

Cost estimates

3a. Budget

Also check the Explanatory Notes accompanying the form.

The maximum amount of a Veni grant is € 250,000 spread over a period of maximum 3 years. If the proposed research is of shorter duration, the maximum amount will be reduced accordingly.

Description		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Total
Staff	FTE** Months				
WP*	Applicant 1fte 36				
NWP*	Scientific programmer .2fte 36	8,177	8,177	8,177	24,531
Total Staff	1.2 72				
Equipment
Total Equipment	
Amazon Web Services	Costs to set up cloud environment and database services	2,500	2,500	2,500	7,500
Total Investments		2,500	2,500	2,500	7,500
Materials	Books	400	200	200	800
Total Materials		400	200	200	800
Travel	Visit to the U.S. for research collaborations	2,500	1,500	1,500	5,500
	Participation at SXSW Conference, Texas	0	1,000	0	1,000
	Travel in The Netherlands (e.g., meeting company representatives)	500	500	500	1,500
Total Travel		3,000	3,000	2,000	8,000
Other	Hosting a workshop on reproducible scientific research (open to other universities); instructor fees	2,500	0	0	2,500
Total Other		2,500	0	0	2,500
Grand total					

- Use for each staff member, type of equipment, type of investment or type of material one row. You can add rows under the (bold print) headings. You cannot add headings.
- Years are Project Years. For example: if your intended starting date is 1 October 2016, then Year 1 ranges from 1 October 2016 to 30 September 2017. Etcetera.

* WP = Scientific Staff; NWP = Non Scientific Staff

** Fill out the time you spend on your Veni (including any FTE that your university may pay for work on your Veni). If your university pays (part of) the time you spend on your Veni you can indicate this in 3b.

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

3b. Cofinancing 'in kind'

Cofinancer/party	Description	Estimated value in Euro
..

3c. Cofinancing 'in cash'

Cofinancer/party	Description	Euro
Tilburg University	Salary costs applicant	

3d. Totals

Grand total	■ (=3a)
Requested budget	250,000 (=3a minus 3b/3c)

3e. Intended starting date (see Notes): September 1, 2016

3f. Have you requested any additional grants for this project either from NWO or from any other institution, and/or has the same idea been submitted elsewhere? yes/no (if 'yes', see Notes)

Yes.

- (1) As a co-applicant, I have submitted a grant proposal (€60,000) to our faculty's management team; €22,500 of this amount could potentially be used to obtain teaching support.

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

Curriculum vitae

4a. Personal details

Title(s), initial(s), first name, surname: dr. H. (Hannes) Datta
Date and place of birth: 4 July 1984, Hildesheim, Germany
Nationality: German

4b. Master's ('doctoraal')

University/College of Higher Education: Maastricht University
Date (dd/mm/yy): 31/8/2010
Main subject: Business Research, M.Sc. (cum laude)

4c. Doctorate

University/College of Higher Education: Maastricht University
Starting date (dd/mm/yy): 01/09/2010
Date of PhD award (dd/mm/yy): 07/02/2014
Supervisor ('Promotor'): prof. Harald J. van Heerde, dr. Bram Foubert, prof. Martin Wetzels
Title of thesis: It's In The Way That You Use It: Usage Behavior, Sales Performance, and Their Interrelationships

4d. Work experience since completing your PhD

Current and previous positions. Specify per appointment: period, number of fte, type of position and institution.

Position	Period (date-date)	Number of fte	Type of position (fixed term, permanent, tenure track, other)	Institution
Assistant Professor	01-09-2013	1.0	Tenure track	Tilburg University

Work experience in months spent since completing your PhD

Please include the calculation (see notes)

Experience	Number of months
Research activities	60% of 23 months = 13.8
Education	40% of 23 months = 9.2
Care or sick leave	0%
Management tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Involvement in data science initiative Planning of new M.Sc. Marketing Analytics
Other, please specify	

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

4e. Academic staff supervised

		Please indicate your (formal) role
PhDs Ongoing	Feedback to about 5 PhD students at my faculty (e.g., on setting up online data collections)	Informal
Completed		
<i>Subtotal PhDs</i>		
Postdocs		
<i>Subtotal postdocs</i>		
Master students	15 (since obtaining my PhD) 30 (during my PhD and as an Assistant Professor)	
<i>Subtotal master students</i>		
Other		
<i>Subtotal other</i>		

4f. Brief summary of research over the last five years

(Max. 250 words)

I have developed and applied econometric models in the areas of access-based services (e.g., free trials for a digital TV service), and digital media (e.g., online piracy).

In my three-year PhD program, I assess how data on consumers' usage behavior can be used to improve managerial decision-making. Given the substantial investment in new data collection methods (web scraping) and high performance computing on the Dutch national eInfrastructure, my PhD consists of two projects. In my first essay, I study the effectiveness of free-trial promotions for customer lifetime value. Using panel data from a digital TV service, I demonstrate permanent behavioral differences, making free-trial customers worth less than regular customers, but more responsive to changes in marketing communication and usage rates. In my second study, I demonstrate that online piracy of music reduces sales, but increases consumer engagement with artists. When accounting for the positive effects of online piracy on engagement, the negative effect of piracy is reduced by 55%.

Throughout my PhD thesis, I make extensive use of advanced econometric techniques. After defending my PhD within 5 months after being appointed at Tilburg University, I have expanded into the area of digital media consumption (e.g., on streaming services), and gained substantial experience working with large data sets and cloud computing. Apart from my interest in new media, I work on two projects in the area of retailing—one on generalizing marketing response elasticities in emerging markets, and one on evaluating the effect of health claims in a grocery shopping context.

[250 words]

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

4g. International activities (see Notes)

Visiting scholar

Waikato University, Hamilton (New Zealand)

- 3 January – 16 April 2012

University of Tübingen (Germany)

- 4-8 February 2013
- 20-23 May 2013

Invited research presentations

- Wageningen University (21 March 2016; scheduled)
- 3rd Symposium on Value Creation in a Changing Customer and Media Environment, Cologne University, Germany (9 July 2015)
- Rijksuniversiteit Groningen (24 June 2014)
- Erasmus University, Rotterdam (17 September 2012)
- Tilburg University (5 September 2012)
- Waikato School of Management, Hamilton, New Zealand (7 February 2012)

International conference Presentations

- Marketing Science, Shanghai (16-18 June 2016; scheduled)
- Marketing Dynamics, Hamburg (6-9 July 2016; scheduled)
- European Marketing Association Conference, Leuven (26-29 May 2015)
- Big Data, Mobile Targeting and Social Media Marketing, LMU Munich (13 March 2015)
- Marketing Dynamics, Stanford University and the University of Chicago, Las Vegas (23 August 2014)
- Marketing Science Conference, Özyeğin University, Istanbul (11-13 July 2013)
- European Marketing Association Conference, Lisbon (22-25 May 2012)
- Marketing Dynamics Conference, Tilburg University (23-25 August 2012)
- Marketing Science Conference, Boston (7-9 June 2012)

International Collaborators

- Harald van Heerde, Research Professor of Marketing, Massey University, New Zealand
- Jan Benedict Steenkamp, Knox Massey Distinguished Professor of Marketing and Area Chair of Marketing, UNC Chapel Hill, USA
- Dominik Papies, Professor of Marketing, Tübingen University, Germany
- Kathleen Cleeren, KU Leuven, Belgium

4h. Other academic activities (see Notes)

Invited conferences

- Invitational Choice Symposium, University of Alberta and University of St. Gallen (14-17 May 2016; scheduled)
- Eurosonic Noorderslag Conference, Groningen (15 January 2016; scheduled)
- Paaspop Academy, Schijndel (3 April 2015)
- Eurosonic Noorderslag Conference, Groningen (15 January 2015)

Ad hoc reviewer for:

- Journal of Marketing Research
- International Journal of Research in Marketing
- Journal of Interactive Marketing
- European Marketing Academy Conference

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

Member of

- INFORMS Society for Marketing Science (ISMS)
- European Marketing Academy (EMAC)

Organizational tasks-Membership:

As an Assistant Professor at Tilburg University

- Conceptualization of new M.Sc. in Marketing Analytics
- Member of Data Science Initiative (development of new B.Sc. Data Science)
- IT-infrastructure committee of the faculty
- Implementation of Google Online Marketing Challenge for M.Sc. students

During PhD at Maastricht University

- Scientific programming support
- Website committee

4i. Scholarships, grants and prizes

Please list the research scholarships/grants and a link to the website for which you have successfully applied and/or prizes that you have won and indicate the amount of money involved. *In case of a consortium grant please specify the amount allocated for your own group or lab.

Scholarship/Grant/ Prize Formal applicant	Amount in euros	*	Year of award
MSI Research Proposal Competition (MSI 4-1854)	\$4,000 (€3,650)		2015
Finalist for the European Marketing Academy Best Paper Award based on a Dissertation (honorable mention)	-		2015
National eInfrastructure (e-infra140195)	Computing infrastructure (20,000 core hours, 1TB storage, worth €1,143 ¹)		2014
National eInfrastructure (e-infra130055)	Computing infrastructure (50,000 core hours, 1TB storage, worth €2,938 ¹)		2013
47 th AMA-Sheth Doctoral Consortium Fellow, Seattle	-		2012
Maastricht Graduate School Travel Grant	€4,000		2012
EMAC Doctoral Colloquium Fellow (Advanced Track)	-		2011
<i>Subtotal</i>	€11,731		
Scholarship/Grant/Prize Formal co-applicant			
<i>Subtotal</i>			
<i>Total</i>	€11,731		

¹ Calculated by SurfSara (correspondence with Frank Heere (frank.heere@surfsara.nl) on December 13, 2015).

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

Output

5a. Output indicators

Please identify the most important output indicators in your field.

Publications: Journal of Marketing Research is considered a top outlet in Marketing.

Order of authors:

- First authors usually contribute the most, and take a significant lead in data preparation, analysis, and writing the paper
- The last author typically has a mentoring role during the project
- Single-authored publications are the exception

5b. Output

Please number your items consecutively and also indicate the total number per category. For publications and letters: only mention those that have been published or have been accepted for publication starting with the most recent publication, do **not** list any forthcoming publications. Please mark key publications that are directly relevant to the proposed research with an S (the S stands for significant).

- **International Refereed articles**

Hannes Datta, Bram Foubert and Harald J. Van Heerde. (2015) The Challenge of Retaining Customers Acquired with Free Trials. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 52(2), 217-234.

- **Selected Work in Progress**

- Datta, Hannes, Bram Foubert and Dominik Papies, "Usage Rates, Facebook Likes, and Online Piracy: Using Big Data to Manage Entertainment Products". Incorporating peer review comments from colleagues. Submission planned within the next month.
- Datta, Hannes, Kathleen Cleeren, Kelly Geyskens and Peter Verhoef, "The Impact of Health Claims on Purchase Decisions". Model estimation phase.
- Datta, Hannes, Marnik G. Dekimpe, Harald J. van Heerde, and Jan Benedict E.M. Steenkamp, "Marketing Effectiveness for Electronic Goods in Emerging Markets". Model estimation phase.

- **Invited lectures**

- B.Sc. Entrepreneurship (prof. dr. Arjan van den Born) (Tilburg University in 2014 and 2015)
- B.Sc. program in Marketing at Waikato University (dr. Valentyna Melnyk, Hamilton, New Zealand in 2012)

5c. Top-publications (see Notes, max. 5)

1. Hannes Datta, Bram Foubert and Harald J. Van Heerde. (2015) The Challenge of Retaining Customers Acquired with Free Trials. *Journal of Marketing Research* (52) 2, 217-234.

5d. Median impact factors for your own field

Compulsory for ZonMw applications. For other NWO divisions, this is only compulsory if you have mentioned impact factors of the journal under question 5a (See Notes).

**Vernieuwingsimpuls
Innovational Research Incentives Scheme
Grant application form 2016**

Please refer to Explanatory Notes when completing this form

Veni scheme

Statements by the applicant

N/A **My thesis manuscript has been approved and I will send the official declaration to NWO.**

(Compulsory for Veni applicants who have not yet received their doctorates, to be sent by post and as a PDF using the electronic system.)

Ethical aspects

	Not applicable	Not yet applied for	Applied for	Received
Approval from a recognised medical ethics review committee	N/A			
Approval from an animal experiments committee	N/A			
Permission for research with the population screening Act	N/A			

If applicable you need to send a copy of (one of) the aforementioned documents to NWO when your application has been granted and before the start of your project.

By signing this form I endorse the code of conduct for laboratory animals and the code of conduct for biosecurity/possibility for dual use of the expected results and will act accordingly if applicable.

- ✓ I have completed this form truthfully.
- ✓ By submitting this document I declare that I satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the *Netherlands Code of Conduct for Scientific Practice 2012*¹ (Association of Universities in the Netherlands)
- ✗ I have submitted non-referees.²

Name: Hannes Datta
Place: Tilburg
Date: 4 January 2016

¹ More information:

[http://www.vsnu.nl/files/documenten/Domeinen/Onderzoek/The Netherlands Code of Conduct for Scientific Practice 2012.pdf](http://www.vsnu.nl/files/documenten/Domeinen/Onderzoek/The_Netherlands_Code_of_Conduct_for_Scientific_Practice_2012.pdf)

² It is possible to indicate non-referees (maximum of three names). The non-referees will NOT be asked to assess your application. Do not incorporate the names in the application. Please submit a separate PDF file with the names of non-referees via the electronic system at the same time as your proposal.

Please submit the application to NWO in electronic form (**PDF format is required!**) using the ISAAC system, which can be accessed via the NWO website (isaac.nwo.nl). The only exception to this rule concerns applications within the Medical Sciences. The Medical Sciences division uses a similar system called ProjectNet, to which access is provided via the division's own website (www.zonmw.nl). For any technical questions regarding submission, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk (isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl).